

**DETERMINANTS OF PREFERENCE OF ABORTION AND NON-UTILIZATION
OF FAMILY PLANNING SERVICES AMONG WOMEN OF CHILDBEARING
AGE IN RURAL COMMUNITIES OF UYO LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA,
AKWA IBOM STATE**

Udom Sunday Daniel¹

Tahirih E. Udousoro²

¹udomdaniel@aksu.edu.ng

08038750959

²thepureone.udousoro@gmail.com

08025433813

Department of Sociology and Anthropology^{1&2}

Akwa Ibom State University, Obio Akpa Campus

ABSTRACT

Abortion rate is related to people's inability, unwillingness and refusal to utilize. The family planning service facilities thus are left with no option but to about their unwanted pregnancies. They reveal that safe and unsafe abortions are both threats to the human lives of both the mother and the embryo who later becomes a child. The study, therefore, noted that the problem of unwanted pregnancies and its consequences could be avoided through the utilization of family planning services thus averting maternal and child mortality in the society. The study which was conducted in rural communities of Uyo, selected eight (8) communities of Etoi and Ikono Clans based on their unique characteristics from the study. It adopted the behaviour option theory and an exploratory and qualitative exploited to collect data from the eighty (80) respondents selected for the study. The study reveals that the poverty level of the people, illiteracy, religious and cultural beliefs, and access to conventional health facilities are all factors that hinder women from utilizing family planning services and thus prefer abortion in cases of unwanted and unplanned programmes. It therefore, recommended awareness programmes to sensitize families on the need to utilize family planning services and the need to avoid abortion, government to provide mobile clinics in communities where hospitals and primary health centres are not established to reduce the burden of transporting private cultural reorientation programmes through the use of media, communities organization and religious groups on the need to do aware with barbaric practices and that are health detrimental.

KEYWORDS: Abortion, Women, Family Planning Services and Childbearing Preference

INTRODUCTION

Abortion is a highly charged emotional subject which involves some highly controversial and complicated issues of law, medicine and morality. Unsafe and safe abortions are both threats to human lives both of the mother and the embryo who later becomes a child. The problem of unwanted pregnancy and its termination is a perennial problem which defies clear-cut answers (Siddique, 2005). Its committal approach could be either through the modern conventional approach of health technology or the traditional herbal approach and is committed mostly by women of childbearing age.

Abortion Law in Nigeria is governed by two laws that differ depending on geographical location. In Northern Nigeria, the law is governed by the penal code Section 232 and in Southern Nigeria, it is governed by the Criminal Code Section 228. The only legal way to have an abortion in Nigeria is if having the child will put the mother's life in danger. Abortion law of the criminal code states that any person who with intent to procure the miscarriage of a woman, whether she is with or is not with a child, unlawfully administers to her or causes her to take poison or other noxious thing or uses any force of any kind, or uses any other means is guilty of a felony and is liable to imprisonment for fourteen years. (Law of Akwa Ibom State, vol. 2)

In a similar manner, the penal code Section 232 states that whoever voluntarily causes a woman with child to miscarry shall, if such miscarriage is not caused in good faith to save the life of the woman, be punished with imprisonment for a term which may extend to fourteen years or with fine or with both. It is then a criminal act of a felony penalty to commit an abortion. Considering its social consequences, abortion poses the risk of being denounced to authority or imprisonment of the woman. It has its impact showing on the well-being of children and other members of the families, from the death of a mother to the stigma experienced by the woman and her family.

According to Ansel, (2014) and Starbird, Maureen and Rachel (2016) family planning is essential in helping women and their male partners to decide freely on whether to have children, how many to have and when to do so, and also improves both maternal and child health.

Family planning is widely acknowledged as an important intervention towards achieving one of the objectives of Sustainable Development Goals. SDGs three (3) focused on ensuring healthy lives and promoting well-being for all ages by 2030, (Ben and Daniel, 2023). Ansel and Milinga (2014) noted that family planning services reduce maternal and child mortality in society through the prevention of unplanned pregnancies and unsafe abortions. Family planning methods such as condom use protect individuals from Sexually Transmitted Infections (STIs) including HIV/AIDs and also reduce unwanted pregnancies while increasing family size as well as enhancing the economic well-being of the family (Daniel, 2016 and 2011). The challenges are always associated with factors such as social, economic, cultural, demographic and environmental which according to Ben, Daniel and Peters (2023) led to a state of confusion and anxiety among pregnant women during the crisis period, making family planning therefore important to avoid cases of unwanted pregnancies and its attendants' consequences.

Family planning has been recognized as a remedy for sex-complicated problems and enhances healthy motherhood with a multiplier favourable socio-economic impact on the

family, society, the nation and the world at large (Inyang-Etoh, 2017). Plan a family requires the application of modern or other methods of birth control in regulating the number, timing and spacing of pregnancies (Debaba, 2010). Family planning allows the couple, particularly the woman, to have control over her fertility without the need for any adjustments in her social and sexual life, (Inyang-Etoh and Abah (2017). It could be deduced that family planning also promotes women's sense of autonomy and their ability to make healthy decisions regarding their livelihood.

United Nations (2020), opined that the utilization of family planning methods by women should be prioritized to reach the attainment of Sustainable Development Goals. To achieve this, emphasis has been on universal access to a full range of safe and reliable family planning methods that would aid couples in realizing their rights to freely and responsibly decide on the number and spacing of their children. Despite quest for availability of such medical services, some are still hoping to have access (Peters *et al.*,2020), which leads to patronage of over -the-counter drugs as alternative (Wilson *et al.*,2020).

The issues related to birth erudition, life and survival of newborn babies have ever received considerable attention in academic research and in socio-economic and health planning (Ben and Daniel, 2023) which emphasizes the need for family planning methods. According to NEEDS (2010) in Udom (2011) Nigerian woman gives birth to an average of five (5) children in their lifetime and the Nigerian government in her commitment along with key stakeholders in 2012 mapped out a series of strategies towards addressing the challenges of population explosion and mortality rate. Daniel (2011) further noted that socio-cultural norms ranging from belief systems, religious creed, women's lack of power as regards sex making, preference for large family size, illiteracy, income status, preference and utilisation of traditional medicine and birth delivery services as well as the problem of accessing medical services all limits the utilisation of family planning services in Ibibio Society.

Deduced from the objectives of Sustainable Development Goals, (Daniel 2011 and 2016) opined that the government is to focus on devolving the financing of its national family planning programmes to state levels. Improve the availability of as well as access to services and facilitate awareness of the need to plan families and slow the rate of its population growth, thus enhancing the path of a healthier future for women and families, through enhancing the provision of family planning services and supplies, as well as enabling an environment in which women and girls make informed choices on their health upon reducing the barriers to family planning utilisation in rural communities.

This, in essence, is due to the importance of newborn to families and society and also because data on the unfortunate incidence of death are pre-requisites for population measurement and health quality of the population, evaluation of the existence of health policies and application of development planning (Ben and Daniel, 2023). Based on the backdrop, this study aims to assess determinants of preference of abortion and the utilization of family planning services among women of childbearing age in rural communities of Uyo Local Government Area.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Behaviour Option Theory

The behaviour option theory attempts to explain the factors that influence the decisions

people make in why they behave the way they do. The theory has it that people's behaviour is a factor in the options available and the cost implications of such behaviour. It explains that people will opt for behaviours which are less costly and are not in conflict with what they believe. Understanding the implications of the options available influences people's choice of behaviour. The theory cites environmental, personal, income level, belief system and behavioural characteristics as the major factors in behavioural determination.

In this study, it is observed that their option for abortion or family is factorised by socio-economic and cultural influences of income status, illiteracy level, belief system, sponge decisions and cost of the options.

It is therefore concluded that people will decide on which option of behaviour to adopt when the options weighed are in cognizance of what they know, their beliefs and their ability to pay for the services.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed an exploratory and qualitative descriptive research approach to explore factors affecting the utilization of family planning services and increased abortion rate among women of childbearing age in rural communities of Uyo Local Government Area. Uyo Local Government Areas comprises four classes namely: Etoi, Offot, Ikono and Oku. Of the four clans of the LGA, two were purposively selected for the study (Etoi and Ikono clans) owing primarily to their inherent rural features in some communities like problems associated with access to proper healthcare and poverty. From each of the clans, ten villages were purposively selected for the study – these villages are mainly rural; a characteristic of interest in this study.

The study selected women of childbearing age who are residents of the villages. Purposive sampling was used to select respondents for inclusion in the study. Women aged between 20 to 50 years, living in rural areas and capable of expressing themselves about the topic under research were selected. Research assistants from the respective villages helped to identify potential study households and respondents in the selected villages.

Data from the respondents were mainly collected using focus group discussions (FGDs). The initial discussions were in English Language and translated into Ibibio to the understanding of all respondents present. The guide deployed consisted of twenty open-ended questions on the perception of abortion and the utilization of family planning services in rural communities of Uyo. In all, eight (8) FGD sessions, four (4) in each of the clans involving a total of eighty (80) participants were held in the selected area. The number of participants in each group was 10.

The essential variables for the study were education, access to health facilities, income levels of families, belief system and age. These were considered important variables in the abortion rate and utilization of family planning services. Before the commencement of the FGDs sessions, the participants were presented with the objectives of the study and both set rules for discussions including effective participation, respect for others' opinions as well as taking turns to speak. Each session lasted for two hours, and to encourage participants' attendance, the discussions were held at the village hall.

RESULTS

No. of respondents 80
 10 in each of the groups.
 NE = No. Education
 YE = Yes Education
 FE = Formal Education
 AM = Abortion Method
 FPM = Family Planning Method

TABLE 1 ETOI CLAN- GROUP 1 AND 2.

COMPONENT VILLA	EDUCATIONAL LEVEL	INCOME STATUS	RELIGIOUS BELIEF	ACCESS TO HEALTH FACILITY	SPOUSE PERMISSION	HAVE UTILIZE FPM	HAVE COMMITTED ABORTION BEFORE
Mbak Etoi	7(NE) 3(YE)	Poor	Their religion does not permit	Far from Home	2 yes/8 No	3	
Ikot Inyang Idung	No FE beyond primary 6	No means of formal income	My pastor says no to it	Far from Home	No	Nil	
Obot Obom	6(NE) 4(YE)	Poor income	I don't believe in it	Cost of transport	No	Nil	
Obio Etoi	7(NE) 4(YE)	Average	My religion encourage it	I do access	2 yes/ 8 no	Have utilize	

Source: Fieldwork (2024)

TABLE 2 IKONO CLAN- GROUP 3 AND 4

COMPONENT VILLAGES	EDUCATIONAL LEVEL	INCOME STATUS	RELIGIOUS BELIEF	ACCESS TO FACILITY	SPOUSE PERMISSION	HAVE UTILIZED FPM	HAVE UTILIZE DAM
Ikot Ekpayak Ikono	6(NE) 4(YE)	Poor	Pastor said no to it but two respondents have utilize it	Distance	2 yes/ 8 no	two respondents have utilize it	7 yes/ 3 no
Ikot OfonIkono	No FE	Poor	Our church does not encourage it	Needs	No	No	9 yes/1 no.
Ikot Ayan Ikono	7(NE) 3(YE)	Poor	Not accepted	Money	1 yes/ 9 no	Only 1 respondent said yes to it	8 yes/2 no
Mbiabong Ikono	7(NE) 3(YE)	Poor	Not accepted	For transport	No	No	8 yes/ 2 no

Source: Fieldwork (2024)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A total number of 80 women of childbearing age from rural areas of the two selected clans in Uyo (Etoi and Ikono) participated in the FGDs. The findings from the FGDs revealed that many factors engender the utilization of the abortion method and reduce the interest in the utilization of family planning services among women of childbearing age in the area. These factors have been grouped under four (4) major headings.

Socio-Demographic Factors:

Three demographic variables were employed; education/literacy level, income status of the family and religious beliefs were found in the study area to have increased the utilization of abortion method and reduction in the utilization of family planning services among women of childbearing age. Again in the cause of the FGDs, the respondents also identify distance to medical facilities, and absence of such facilities in their community as another factor that affects their utilization of family planning services, and preference of abortion as well as family planning method.

Education/Literacy Level:

The findings revealed the problem of awareness on the part of the participants in their perception and utilization of family planning services. They blamed their non-utilization of the services to their poor level of education as well as that of their husbands. The women submitted that it was their low level of education that served as a barrier for them to comprehend and utilize family planning information, and services thus considers their inability to understand their cycle calendar. According to the FGDs findings,

“...we are affected by the level of our educational attainment as it is difficult for us to read the documents we are given to follow. Our community too does not give the needed awareness as we do not have health workers who comes around to educate us on what to do. It is equally difficult to make use of the calendar as each time we are able to visit the health centre we are told to follow our calendar and we do not know how to do that”.

In the same vein, the study revealed that some women refused to utilize the services in preference of abortion because their parents told them of the dangers of family planning services.

“...I don't utilize family planning services because my mother said it will not allow me to be healthy and to have my children when I wish to do that, that it causes the growth of fibroid in women and thus can cause infertility among women and so I chose the abortion because I can get pregnant again”.

However, discussion with women who have attended higher education revealed that education enabled them to make informed decisions as regards the study topic and to be aware of and equally utilize the different family planning methods. They submitted that their ability to read and write helped them to follow and utilize the different family planning literature given to them at the health centres and therefore overcome the dangers perceived of family planning by family members and close persons.

“ We utilize family planning methods and we have not had any health effects as we were told by our illiterate parents and friends. It keeps us away from the dangers of abortion. Family planning helped us to decide when to have a child, enabled us to regain our health after delivery, gives us time for personal advancement and prevents unplanned pregnancies and STDs”.

The literate women group stated that they can read the calendar thus helping them to know their evolution period and when to stay away from sex and unwanted pregnancy.

Findings deduced from the discussion on educational variables revealed that poor educational attainment influences perception and poor utilization of family planning services and the preference for abortion among women of childbearing age in rural areas of Uyo Local Government Area.

Income status of the family

The income status of the family was also identified as the determinant factor affecting the perception of women and in the long run influences utilization of family planning services in the study area thus influencing their involvement in abortion. Information gathered during the focus group discussion revealed that the respondent's utilization of modern family planning methods was limited by their level of income.

In one of the group discussions the participant explained.....

“We are not able to utilize the modern family planning services because of its cost implications. Apart from the cost of transportation, you need to buy some drugs and again pay for other service charges, and where do we get such funds from? We don't even have money to feed our children and pay their school fees. It is difficult with us; how do we raise money for family planning”....

Discussion from the group further revealed that the level of unemployment in the area is a serious hindrance to the utilization of family planning services. Our husband do not have a reliable income, we are not gainfully employed and in most cases it is difficult to buy a malaria drugs from patent medicine stores, how then do we go for family planning services that is why abortion is rather referred, because we only need herbs to evacuate it. We rely on our farms products and animals for our sustenance. We are aware of the modern family planning methods, but cannot utilize it because of our income level. The respondents further submit thus;

“government should make family planning services free for women of reproductive age in our community. It will save us from the danger of abortion, some of our young ladies have died untimely because of trying to abort unwanted pregnancies. If we are at least able to get our ways to the hospital we should be attended to free.

In summary, the findings identified cost of drugs, transportation to access the services, and the cost of other services as being the burden of family planning services in the area of study”.

Religious/Belief System

The focus group discussions, also identified religious and belief systems as other factors that affect the utilization of family planning services in preference of abortion among women of child bearing age in the rural area of Uyo. The study revealed that some religious groups do not approve their members to utilize the services and this affects their perception about family planning. We secretly take to abortion to stay off stigmatization.

In one of the FGD sessions a participant stated as follows;

We don't utilize the services because my pastor said God does not approve of it and that was why god killed a man who applied the withdrawal method in the bible. According to this group, God will kill any person who utilizes family planning services and as such we don't practice it in order to disassociate ourselves from God's punishment but some women take to abortion when they have unwanted pregnancies

The discussion further revealed that according to the bible,
“Children are in heritage from God and Jesus commanded that no man should hinder them”.

Some of the participants believe that the act of family planning is a process of hindering the heritage of God. This is against God's design so we don't utilize it. Some people believe that it is the strategy of the government to make some religious groups more populated than others.

However, another set of respondents noted that the fear of the loss of some children to death makes them have more than four children. One of the participants reported that:

The God who gives it can decide to take some, so you need a reasonable number of children in case, the giver decides to take some.

These people believe that if God can decide to take Isaac from Abraham he can choose any other child, and therefore you need more children in case of such demand from God.

CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATIONS

The study on the preference of abortion and non-utilization of family planning services among women of childbearing age in rural communities of Uyo Local Government Area shows that there is high level of engagement in abortion. The study opined that maternal mortalities are caused by the process of illegal abortions because they are frequently performed by those who are not competent to do the job and through the use of over-the-counter drugs. Married women and single girls are exposed to the risk of abortion since they lack the knowledge of the right medical practitioner to approach. For the young reproductive ladies in the rural communities of the Uyo Local Government Area, the causes of abortion may be more compelling for them as they seek the services of a non-qualified person. Emergency

steps are not sometimes possible in some abortions because they are performed in clandestine manner.

Pregnancy challenges are always associated with factors such as social, economic, medical, cultural, demographic and the environment. A catalogue of some of these related challenges that affect women while in pregnancy bothered the economic status of the family, parental pressure, high ambition, belief system, location of hospitals et cetera.

Measures such as identification and formulation of the research problem and objectives, selection of study participants and accuracy in data collection, analysis and interpretation helped to ensure the validity and reliability of the findings. Audio recordings and field notes captured all the discussions during data collection. The study identified cultural practices as a hindrance to family planning services, poor awareness patterns and illiteracy of the people on the need to utilize family planning services were identified as a push to abortion practices by women in rural areas. Thus the study recommended the need for more awareness programmes for women on the dangers of abortion and mobile clinics for medical services in rural areas a reduced rate.

REFERENCES

- Afzal Qadri, S. M. (2005), Criminology, Eastern Book Company, Lucknow.
- Ahmad Siddique (2005) criminology, Eastern Book Company, Lucknow
- Anasel, M. G. (2014). Family Planning Programme Implementation; Differences in Contraceptive Prevalence Rates Across Local Government Authorities in Tanzania.
- Anasel, M. G. and Milinga U. J. (2014). Determinants of Contraceptive use among married women in Tanzania; Policy Implication. *African Population Studies*, 976-988.
- Ben, V. E., Daniel, U. S. and Peters, M. I. (2023). Estimation of Life Expectancies among pregnant women during Covid-19 in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Culture and Society*, Maiden Edition.
- Ben, V. E. and Daniel, U. S. (2023). Disease Prevalence and Infant Mortality in the Rural Areas of Akwa Ibom State. *AKSU Annuals of Sustainable Development*, 1(2): 3027-0499.
- Daniel, U. S. (2011). An Assessment of National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategies in Uyo Local Government Area. M.Sc. Dissertation, Research gate.
- Daniel, U. S. (2016). Population Growth and Social Services Propulsion in Uyo Senatorial District of Akwa Ibom State Publicity PhD Thesis Research Gate.
- Debaba Y. (2010). Child Spacing and Fertility Planning Behaviour among Women in Manna District Jumna Zone, South West Ethiopia. *Ethiopian Journal of Health Science*, 20:83-90.
- Ministry of Justices, (2000), Law of Akwa Ibom State. Millhaus publishing Ltd, Nigeria.
- Peters, M. I., Bassey, A. E. and Nya, A. (2020). Still Hoping for Medical Prescribe Drugs: Unveiling the Experiences of Farmers in Farm Settlement Areas of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Perspectives on Drugs, Alcohol and Society in Africa. In: Abiyoke and Obot (Eds). A Publication of CRISA. Uyo. 5 (2020).
- Starbird E., Maureen, N. and Rachel M. (2016). Investing in Family Planning; Key to Achieving the Sustainable Development Goals. *Global Health Science and Practice*, 4(2):191-210.
- Wilson, N. U., Usoroh, R. O. and Peters, M. I. (2020). Unorthodox Use of Orthodox Drugs Use among Rural Women in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Perspectives on Drugs, Alcohol and Society in Africa. In: Abiyoke and Obot (Eds). A Publication of CRISA. Uyo. 5 (2020).